

THE INFLUENCE OF PRINCIPAL LEADERSHIP AND PRINCIPAL PROFESSIONALISM ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STATE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN TANGERANG REGENCY

SUTARMAN

Sheikh Yusuf Tangerang Islamic University. Email: sutarman@unis.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to analyze the influence of the Principal's leadership on teacher performance, the influence of the Principal's professionalism on teacher performance and the influence of leadership and professionalism together on teacher performance. This research uses a statistical quantitative approach. The population of all SD Negeri 4 teachers is 246 people, with a sample size of 142 people. Data collection techniques through questionnaires. Analysis of the results used statistics, simple regression and multiple regression and used SPSS Windows Version 14. The research results showed that the leadership of the principal at SD Negeri 4 was in the good category with a score of 58.8030, professionalism in the good category. Professional category 58.0915, good teacher performance 61.4155. Simple regression analysis shows a positive and significant influence of principal leadership on public elementary school teacher performance of 25.0%, professionalism has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance with a coefficient of determination of 39.5%. The results of multiple regression analysis show a positive and significant influence simultaneously between the leadership and professionalism of school principals towards teachers on the performance of state elementary school teachers with a coefficient of determination of 45.0%.

Keywords: Principal Leadership, Professionalism, Teacher Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Elementary school principals as organizational leaders need to master and have the ability to motivate their subordinates, so that elementary school principals can influence their subordinates, they must understand what their subordinates need. Agung, W. (2020). Therefore, school principals as leaders in an organization should be aware of and responsive to techniques to maintain teacher performance and job satisfaction, including 6 encouraging teachers so they can carry out their duties by the rules and directions.

Good work performance can be influenced by skills and motivation, skills without motivation or motivation without skills will not produce high output Yawan, Ruth. (2016). Regional Productivity Development Center, explains that two important factors influence employee performance, namely; (1) mental attitude in the form of work motivation, work discipline, and work ethics; (2) management leadership.

Leadership will be able to differentiate the characteristics of an organization from other organizations. Dynamic and effective leadership is the most basic potential and is difficult to find, but this does not mean that a leader is incapable of becoming a leader with dynamic and effective leadership. Baldy, M. Y. (2019). By understanding leadership theory, you will be able to increase your understanding of yourself, know your potential weaknesses and strengths, and

will be able to increase your understanding of how you should treat your subordinates. Teacher performance is a teacher's ability to carry out actions by predetermined goals, which include aspects of planning teaching and learning programs, implementing the teaching and learning process, creating and maintaining optimal classes, controlling optimal learning conditions, and assessing learning outcomes. Erhan, A. N. J. (2019). Performance is very important in determining the quality of someone's work, including a teacher.

Framework of Thinking

This case, teacher achievement is the behavior of teachers who have (1) Skills 16 and master all the ins and outs of their field of duty and other fields related to their duties. (2) Excellent skills in carrying out their duties. (3) Extensive experience in the field of duties and other fields related to the duties. (4) Always serious and timeless in carrying out his duties. (5) Good physical and spiritual freshness and health. (6) Always carry out tasks efficiently and effectively. (7) The work results far exceed the specified average work results. Mahmudi. (2019). both in terms of quality and in terms of quantity.

Work Performance Can be Determined Through

- a. **Work Skills** Work skills are concrete actions carried out by teachers in mastering their field of work both in supervision and in actions supervision by other parties. As proof of his work skills, he can work is always serious, and carries out his duties efficiently and effectively.
- b. **Quality of work:** Quality of work is a real value that can be seen after carrying out work, both abstract and concrete. The quality of work can be seen as always doing good and correct things without making significant mistakes and achieving results that are quite good and adequate even though corrections are needed from certain parties.
- c. **Development** Development is a work step to be able to develop the ideas you have for the progress of the organization. In development, always show an attitude and interest that wants to progress and always use an appropriate evaluation system.
- d. **Fortitude** is a characteristic possessed by a teacher in facing work, whether categorized as difficult or categorized as light/easy. In steadfastness, you can see the characteristic of not giving up quickly in facing complicated problems, not liking to cause chaos, and always repeating work that is said to have not been successful.
- e. Teachers who have good work performance will always work without being absent. After arriving, he routinely filled in the attendance register considering that his profession was the most prioritized job.
- f. **Behavior** is an individual attitude that a person has in carrying out their duties, which includes this attitude, including always obeying legal and official regulations, having a polite, flexible, firm, and wise attitude, not distinguishing between superiors and co-workers, and having a tendency to provide services by their field of duties.

Figure 1: Causality Relationship between the Variables Studied

RESEARCH METHODS

This quantitative research seeks systematic empirical data and in this research, the researcher cannot directly control the independent variables because the events have already happened and by their nature cannot be manipulated.

Population

The population in this study were all state elementary school teachers in the Assisted Region in Tangerang, Uno, B. Hamzah. (2016). consisting of 50 state elementary schools with a total of 244 teachers with Civil Servant status.

Sample

Considering that the population is quite large, this research uses a sample. The sample size was determined using the Krejcie table (Sugiyono, 2018). Based on the Krejcie table, if the population is 246 then the sample is 142. Thus, the sample in this study is 142 teachers at regional elementary schools assisted by Tangerang City.

Table 1: Research Sample Size

No. - Number of Elementary Schools Sample Population 1 I 7 65 38 2 II 7 57 33 3 III 7 63 36 4 IV 7 61 35 Total 28 246 142

No	Built Area	Number of elementary schools	Population	Samples
1.	I	7	65	38
2.	II	7	57	33
3.	III	7	63	36
4.	IV	7	61	35
Amount		28	246	142

Research variable

In this research three variables are grouped into two, namely the independent variable/predictor and the dependent variable/criterion. Variables are seen as variables that are thought to influence the independent variable. The independent variables consist of the principal's leadership as perceived by the teacher (X1), and teacher professionalism (X2). Meanwhile, the dependent variable is teacher performance (Y).

Operational Definition of Variables

There are three operational definitions of variables that will be presented, namely operational definitions of principal leadership variables (X1), principal leadership professionalism (X2), and teacher performance at - IV Elementary School, Tangerang Regency (Y) as follows:

Principal Leadership (X1)

Principal leadership is the pattern of behavior of the principal in organizing and directing teachers so that this behavior describes the interaction between the school and its subordinates and is measured using indicators; (1) having a strong personality, (2) understanding the conditions of teachers, employees and students, (3) have a vision and understand the mission of the school, (4) the ability to make decisions, (5) the ability to communicate.

Principal Leadership Professionalism (X2)

The professionalism of school principal leadership means a form of commitment by members of a profession to always improve and develop their competence with the aim of ensuring that their professional quality in running and leading all existing resources in a school is willing to work together to improve school quality.

Teacher Performance (Y)

Teacher performance is the ability of a teacher or a teacher's performance in carrying out their duties which can be measured by the following indicators: (1) ability to prepare teaching programs, (2) ability to analyze learning, (4) ability to prepare learning enrichment programs (5) ability to prepare activity programs for mentoring.

DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

The results of statistical calculations on the teacher performance variables (Y), principal leadership (X1), and principal leadership professionalism (X2) can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of statistical calculations on research variables

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Y	61.4155	4.49625	142
X1	58.8030	4.26970	142
X2	58.0915	4.73990	142

In the teacher performance variable, the mean result is 61.4155 with a standard deviation of 4.49625. The principal's leadership variable has a mean of 58.8030 with a standard deviation of 4.26970 and the principal's professionalism variable is 58.0915 with a standard deviation of 4.73990.

Description of Teacher Performance Variables

The teacher performance variable includes 15 research instrument questions with 5 choices so that the item scores can be determined as follows.

- a. Highest score $5 \times 15 = 75$
- b. Lowest score $1 \times 15 = 15$
- c. Range = 60
- d. Class interval = $75 : 5 = 15$

A detailed description of the performance of - IV Public Elementary School teachers in Tangerang Regency based on the absolute criteria that have been determined can be seen in Table 2 as follows.

Table 2: Description of Teacher Performance at SD Negeri - IV, Tangerang Regency

No.	Interval	Criteria	Frequency	Percentage
1	64 – 75	Very good	35	24,0
2	52 – 63	Good	95	65,5
3	41 – 52	Pretty good	15	10,5
4	39 – 40	Not good	0	0
5	27 – 38	Not good	0	0
Percentage			145	100

The performance of - State Elementary School teachers in Tangerang Regency. According to teacher perceptions, respectively, very good 23.9%, good 65.5%, quite good 10.6%. Meanwhile, the mean or average score obtained was 61.4155 which was located in the interval 52-63 in the good category. Thus, the performance of - IV State Elementary School teachers, Tangerang Regency is good.

Figure 1 Tangerang Regency Public Elementary School

Description of Principal Leadership Variables

The principal leadership variable contains 15 questions on the research instrument with 5 choices so that the item score can be determined as follows.

- Highest score $5 \times 15 = 75$
- Lowest score $1 \times 15 = 15$
- Range = 60
- Class interval = $75 : 5 = 15$

There is a detailed description of the leadership of the principal of SD Negeri - IV, Tangerang Regency. Based on the normative criteria established in Chapter III, it can be seen in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3: Description of Leadership of the Principal of SD Negeri - IV, Tangerang Regency

No.	Intervals	Criteria	Frequency	Percentage
1	64 – 75	Very good	25	18,5
2	52 – 63	Good	102	72,5
3	41 – 52	Pretty good	15	10,0
4	39 – 40	Not good	0	0
5	27 – 38	Not good	0	0
Amount			142	100

The leadership of the principal of state elementary school - IV, Tangerang Regency, according to teachers' perceptions, was respectively very good 18.3%, good 72.0%, quite good 9.9%, and those who said it was not good and not good, There isn't any. Meanwhile, the mean or average score obtained was 58.8930 which was located in the interval 58 – 63 in the good category.

Figure 2: Percentage of Principal Leadership at SD Negeri IV Tangerang Regency

Description of Teacher Professionalism Variables

The variable teacher professionalism in the research instrument consists of 15 questions with 5 choices so that the item score can be determined as follows.

- a. Highest score $5 \times 15 = 75$
- b. Lowest score $1 \times 15 = 15$
- c. Range = 60
- d. Class interval = $60 : 5 = 12$

The results of this descriptive analysis, when depicted in pie chart form, can be seen in Figure 3 below

Figure 3: The Percentage of Teacher Professionalism in SD Negeri IV Tangerang Regency

Requirements Test Results

In analyzing, regression is used, first testing the requirements for the variables studied. The test requirements in question are:

Normality Test

The data were analyzed to test the hypothesis and first tested the level of normality by calculating the Kolmogorov Smirnov Goodness of F-Test with SPSS. The results of the analysis can be seen in Table 4 below

Table 4: Data Normality Test Results

NPar Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Y
N		142
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	61.4155
	Std. Deviation	4.44962
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.213
	Positive	.213
	Negative	-.132
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		2.540
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.217

a. Test distribution is Normal.

MODEL: MOD_1.

- a. Distribution tested: Normal
- b. Proportion estimation formula used: Blom's Rank assigned to ties: Mean

Based on the calculation of the Kolmogorov Smirnov one sample Goodness of Fit Test output, the significance value is $0.215 = 21.5\%$, so it is greater than 5% or ($21.75\% > 5\%$), so the null hypothesis is accepted, with the dependent variable being a normal distribution. The test results meet the requirements with regression analysis.

Gambar 4: P-Plot Hasil Uji Normalitas

Hypothesis Test Results

The Influence of Principal Leadership (X1) on Teacher Performance (Y)

The principal's leadership and teacher performance have a significant effect, as shown by the t-count = 6.980 > t-table 0.05 (df = 140) of 1.645. With the results of a simple t-test regression on teacher performance which is determined by the principal's leadership. The t-test results are based on the SPSS output below.

Coefficient^s

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	29.946	4.519		6.627	.000
	X1	0.535	0.077	0.508	6.982	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on the table above, the regression coefficient is 0.535 and the constant is 29.945. There is an influence of the principal's leadership variable on teacher performance in the form of a regression equation $Y = 29.945 + 0.535X1$. If the principal's leadership increases by one point, teacher performance increases by 0.535 points with a constant of 29.945. So the better the principal's leadership and the teacher's performance will also increase. The F-test results are $\text{Sig } 0.000 < 0.05$. That regression can estimate teacher performance which can have a positive and significant influence.

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	736.195	1	736.195	48.750	.000 ^a
	Residual	2114.295	140	15.100		
	Total	2850.485	141			

a. Predictors: (Constant), X1

b. Dependent Variable: Y

The magnitude of the influence of the principal's leadership on teacher performance can be seen in the following computer output

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.508 ^a	.258	.253	3.88614	2.095

a. Predictors: (Constant), X1

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on SPSS calculations, the R-square value is 0.260. That the principal's leadership variable influences teacher performance, namely 26.0%, there is a remainder of 74.2%.

The Influence of Professionalism (X2) on Teacher Performance (Y)

Based on SPSS analysis, the correlation coefficient is obtained, namely 0.625. The influence of the principal's professionalism on teacher performance is significant, that the t-value = $9.535 > 0.05$ ($df = 140$) is 1.645. The results of the t-test with simple regression show that teacher performance is determined by the professionalism of the school principal.

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26.837	3.638		7.377	.000
	X2	.595	.062	.627	9.536	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on the calculation of the regression coefficient = 0.595 and constant = 26.835. There is an influence on the two variables of principal professionalism on teacher performance, namely the regression equation $Y = 26.835 + 0.595X2$. If the professionalism of the principal increases by one point, the teacher's performance increases = 0.595 points. The influence is linear, with F-test results = Sig 0.000 < 0.05

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1122.380	1	1122.380	90.930	.000 ^a
	Residual	1728.105	140	12.345		
	Amount	2850.485	141			

a. Predictors: (Constant), X2

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on calculations, the R-square value = 0.395. That the principal's professionalism variable influences teacher performance = 39.5%, and the remaining = 60.6% is determined by a simple regression model with partial tests. The professionalism of the school principal has a dominant influence compared to the leadership of the school principal. The influence of principal professionalism on teacher performance is significant with the F-test Sig 0.000 < 0.05.

The Influence of Principal Leadership (X1) and Principal Professionalism (X2) on Teacher Performance (Y)

To examine the influence of principal leadership and principal professionalism on teacher performance using multiple linear regression. With SPSS 14, the following is obtained

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	18.670	4.295		4.345	.000
X1	.260	.080	.247	3.310	.001
X2	.470	.070	.498	6.670	.000

Based on SPSS 14 regression calculations, the following multiple regression equation is obtained with Constant = 18.670, with the principal's leadership coefficient (X1) = 0.260, and the principal's professionalism coefficient (X2) = 0.470. With the regression equation, namely $Y = 18.670 + 0.260 X1 + 0.470 X2$.

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1248.763	2	624.381	54.185	.000 ^a
Residual	1601.723	139	11.523		
Total	2850.486	141			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1
b. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on SPSS 14 analysis, the principal's leadership and the principal's professionalism have a significant effect on teacher performance, with F-test results = 54.185 > F-alpha distribution = 0.05 (df= 2: 140) = 3.00 or Sig 0.00 < 0.00.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.662 ^a	.438	.430	3.39458	2.018

- a. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1
b. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on SPSS 14 analysis, the R-square value obtained = 0.438. So the variables of principal leadership and professionalism of the principal influence teacher performance together = 44.0%, and the remaining = 56.0% is determined by other factors not studied.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, several conclusions can be drawn, including the following

- 1) The results of statistical calculations show that the teacher performance variable obtained a mean of = 61.4155 with a good category = 65.50%, the principal's leadership obtained = 58.8030 with a good category = 71.80% and the principal's professionalism obtained a mean = 58, 0915 with good category. teacher performance category = 77.5%.
- 2) Has a positive and significant influence on the principal's leadership on teacher performance, namely = 25.80%. If the principal's leadership improves, teacher performance will also increase.

- 3) The professionalism of the school principal has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance, namely = 39.40%. So if the school principal becomes more professional, the teacher's performance will also increase.
- 4) Has a positive and significant influence on the principal's leadership and principal's professionalism on teacher performance, namely = 43.80%. So if the principal's leadership and professionalism increase, teacher performance will also increase.

SUGGESTION

Based on the discussion and conclusions, several recommendations can be made, namely as follows:

- 1) For leadership, the principal as a leader in the school must continuously strive and empower all teachers so that teacher performance increases through teacher competency, improving skills, especially in learning media, because teacher performance is not optimal, namely = 10.5%.
- 2) The professionalism of school principals must be improved, because there are still teachers in Tangerang Regency Public Elementary Schools who are inadequate and less professional in carrying out their duties. So that teachers want to upgrade their education to a higher level, and increase their skills through training

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